

Template synthesis of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 14- and 16-membered tetraazamacrocycles

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Complexes of the types [ML(NO₃)₂]NO₃ (M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}), [ML(NO₃)₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}), [CuL]Cl₂ and [ZnL]Cl₂ (where L = tetraazamacrocycle having 14- or 16-membered ring) have been synthesized by the condensation of 2,3-hexanedione with 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,4-diaminobutane in the presence of metal ions as templates.

Transition metal complexes of a large number of macrocycles derived from α - or β -diketones have been reported. Mohamed *et al.*¹ synthesized Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 14- and 16-membered tetraazamacrocycles by the template condensation of dibenzoylmethane with diaminoalkanes. Singh *et al.*² reported Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cr^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes of 5,7,12,14-tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-4,7,11,14-tetraene. Curtis³ prepared Ni^{II} complexes of *rac*- and *meso*-5,12-dimethyl-7,14-diphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-4,11-diene. Shakir *et al.*⁴ reported Cr^{II}, Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 5,12-dioxo-7,14-dimethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-4,11-diene. By [2 + 2] cyclocondensation of 2,3-butanedione with 1,3-diaminopropane using metal ions as templates, Rose *et al.*⁵ synthesized Fe^{II}, Co^{III} and Cu^{II} complexes of tetraaza-macrocycles. We reported earlier⁶ template synthesis of Cr^{III} and Zn^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from 2,3-butanedione and diaminoalkanes. In the present paper Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 14- and 16-membered tetraazamacrocycles [I, L¹ and L²] derived from 2,3-

hexanedione and 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,4-diamino-butane are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of metal salts with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,4-diaminobutane in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios resulted in the formation of complexes of 14- and 16-membered tetraazamacrocycles (Scheme 1).

M	X	k	m	x	Coordination no.
Cr	NO ₃	3	1	9	6
Fe	NO ₃	3	1	9	6
Co	NO ₃	2	0	6	6
Ni	NO ₃	2	0	6	6
Cu	Cl	2	2	2	4
Zn	Cl	2	0	0	6

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

I	
"	
L ¹	3
L ²	4

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids and stable at room temperature. On heating these complexes do not melt but decompose. These are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, acetone, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform, but soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. The analytical data and physico-chemical characteristics of these complexes are recorded in Table 1.

Eggleston and Jackels⁷ have ruled out the possibility of the formation of [1 + 1] condensation products, such as diazepine, during the template synthesis of Fe^{II}, Co^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-3,10-diphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene, on the basis of ¹H

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of macrocyclic complexes*

Compd./ Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	Cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
[CrL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Grey	200	9.43 (9.58)	99	4.13
[CrL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Grey	190	8.99 (9.11)	113	4.10
[FeL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Brown	191	10.39 (10.22)	117	5.84
[FeL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃ Brown	190	9.67 (9.72)	115	5.79
[CoL ^I (NO ₃) ₂] Brown	125	12.16 (12.09)	61	4.23
[CoL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂] Green	122	11.49 (11.43)	80	5.11
[NiL ^I (NO ₃) ₂] Purple	195	12.13 (12.05)	77	3.88
[NiL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂] Green	110	11.51 (11.39)	82	4.28
[CuL ^I]Cl ₂ Blue	172	14.34 (14.47)	56	2.07
[CuL ^{II}]Cl ₂ Green	138	13.71 (13.60)	81	2.02
[ZnL ^I]Cl ₂ White	230	14.92 (14.84)	9	Diamag.
[ZnL ^{II}]Cl ₂ White	224	13.83 (13.94)	19	Diamag.

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and Cl analyses.

NMR studies. The M–N bond lengths, for which the strain energy is minimum in the transition metal complexes of 12- to 16-membered saturated tetraazamacrocycles, have been calculated in the range 1.8–2.4 Å indicating that macrocycles of varying ring sizes coordinate readily to transition metal ions to give stable complexes⁸. There will be greater flexibility in the larger ring due to which metal ions smaller than the macrocyclic ring size can also be conveniently accommodated resulting in the formation of stable complexes. Formation constants and molecular mechanics calculations have shown that chelate ring size is important in controlling metal ion size based selectivity than the macrocyclic ring size and there is very small effect of macrocyclic ring size on the stability of the complexes due to the flexibility of large ring macrocycles⁹.

None of the present macrocyclic complexes exhibited any absorption at 1700 or 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ due to unreacted >C=O or –NH₂ group. In Fe^{II}, Co^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of an N₆O₄ macrocycle, Nelson *et al.*¹⁰ reported absence of bands at 1700 or 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ which could be assigned to residual keto or amine group. All the reported complexes

of the present investigations show a strong band in the region 1580–1640 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to coordinated >C=N group. In the IR spectra of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{III} complexes of macrocycles derived from carbohydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine, bands at 1580–1640 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹¹. All the reported macrocyclic complexes containing nitrate exhibit absorption bands at 1380 and 810–820 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to ionic nitrate¹¹. Bands at 1010–1040 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to coordinated nitrate group, and the appearance of bands at 1460–1550 cm⁻¹ confirms the monodentate coordination mode of the nitrate group¹². In the IR spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, appearance of bands due to coordinated as well as ionic nitrate indicates that the nitrate groups are weakly coordinated.

The electronic spectra of Cr^{III} complexes exhibit bands at ~16530, ~25000 and ~26700 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(a)$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(b)$ or ${}^4B_{2g}$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions respectively¹¹. The Fe^{III} complexes show three bands at ~13700, ~16400 and ~25000 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ transitions respectively¹¹. The cobalt(II) complexes exhibit bands at ~11000, ~16400 and ~19000 cm⁻¹ due to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively¹³. The nickel(II) complexes exhibit bands at ~9800, 16400 and ~27000 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively¹⁴. The electronic spectra of these complexes are consistent with the distorted octahedral geometry with D_{4h} symmetry. The copper(II) complexes show a characteristic broad band at ~16400 cm⁻¹ due to ligand field transitions¹⁵. This broad band contains all the possible $d-d$ transitions and is consistent with the square planar geometry for copper(II) complexes. All the complexes show intense charge transfer bands at ~29400 cm⁻¹ or above.

Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO are recorded in Table 1. Molar conductances of Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes are typical of 3 : 1 electrolytes¹⁶ indicating that the coordinated nitrate groups are replaced by solvent molecules. Conductance values for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes correspond to 2 : 1 electrolytes, indicating that both the coordinated anions are displaced by solvent molecules¹⁷. Cu^{II} complexes behave as 2 : 1 electrolytes. Molar conductances of Zn^{II} complexes are very low showing them to be non electrolytes.

The μ_{eff} values of the reported metal complexes of macrocycles are recorded in Table 1. For Cr^{III} complexes, magnetic moments are 4.13 and 4.10 B.M. which are in accordance with the spin only value for three unpaired elec-

trons and are characteristic of high spin octahedral chromium(III) complexes. For Cr^{III} complexes of 1,4,8,12-tetraazacyclopentadecane with imido axial ligands (anions of succinimide or phthalimide), Islam *et al.*¹⁸ reported the magnetic moments 3.92 and 4.12 B.M. respectively. Fe^{III} macrocyclic complexes have magnetic moments 5.84 and 5.79 B.M. indicating the high spin state of Fe^{III}. These complexes may possess octahedral geometry. Fe^{III} complexes of dibenzotetraazamacrocycles have been reported to possess magnetic moments in the range 5.71–6.19 B.M.¹⁹ For Co^{II} complexes μ_{eff} values are 4.23 and 5.11 B.M. suggesting high spin state of Co^{II}. μ_{eff} values of 3.88 and 4.28 B.M. for Ni^{II} complexes indicate the presence of two unpaired electrons and the geometry may be octahedral. Higher values of magnetic moments for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes may be due to large orbital contribution²⁰. Cu^{II} complexes possess magnetic moments 2.07 and 2.02 B.M. which correspond to one unpaired electron. For Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from dihydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine Rana *et al.*²¹ reported magnetic moments in the range 4.48–4.65, 2.96–3.10 and 1.78–1.88 B.M. respectively. Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

¹H NMR spectrum of one representative Zn^{II} complex (II) was recorded. The α -CH₂ protons of the amine residue give a triplet at δ 2.75 ppm due to coupling with the β -CH₂ protons. The β -CH₂ protons of the amine residue give a broad peak at δ 1.67 ppm. In macrocyclic precursor, 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (III), the α -CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.63 ppm and β -CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm²². The free macrocycle has not been isolated during the present investigations but it is expected to exhibit the α - and β -CH₂ protons almost at the same position as reported for III. As compared to III, in Zn^{II} complex of the macrocycle, the peaks due to α - and β -CH₂ protons are observed at higher fields. Highfield shift of these protons confirms the coordination of the nitrogen atoms of the macrocycle to Zn^{II}. The CH₃^(a) protons of the *n*-propyl group of ketone residue give rise to a triplet at δ 1.0 ppm due to coupling with the CH₂^(b)

protons. The CH₂^(b) protons give a broad peak at δ 1.48 ppm, CH₂^(c) protons a triplet at δ 2.16 ppm and CH₃^(d) protons a singlet at δ 1.98 ppm.

Experimental

Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, ZnCl₂ (all Fluka), Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Merck), CuCl₂·2H₂O (B.D.H.) and 2,3-hexanedione (Aldrich) were used as supplied. 1,3-Diaminopropane and 1,4-diaminobutane (both Fluka) and *n*-butanol were distilled before use.

The chromium, iron, cobalt, nickel, copper and zinc contents of the reported complexes were determined following the conventional methods. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method, while chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl. IR spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded (400–4000 cm⁻¹) on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Jasco-7800 UV-VIS spectrophotometer at Mohan Lal Sukhadia University, Udaipur. Conductances were measured at room temperature in DMSO by Systronics 304 conductivity meter. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature using a Gouy balance at Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali, Rajasthan. ¹H NMR spectrum (DMSO-*d*₆) was recorded on a Bruker-300 NMR spectrometer at Biocryst Pharmaceutical Inc., Birmingham, Alabama (U.S.A.) using TMS as a reference.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (1.0 mmol) was dissolved in *n*-butanol (20 ml) with stirring and 2,3-hexanedione (2.0 mmol in ~15 ml *n*-butanol) was added. 1,3-Diaminopropane or 1,4-diaminobutane (2.0 mmol in ~15 ml *n*-butanol) was added to the above mixture dropwise with constant stirring and the stirring continued for ~5 h. The resulting solid was washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Similarly, reactions of Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O and ZnCl₂ with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,4-diaminobutane were carried out and the corresponding complexes were isolated (yields 41–69%).

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